

Optical Resolution of Some α - and γ -Substituted Pyridine Methanols

K. A. Thakar and U. S. Pathak

Several tertiary alcohols, as listed in Table I, have been successfully prepared by the interaction of 2- and 4-benzoylpyridine and the appropriate Grignard reagent according to Kenyon and Thakar¹. These tertiary alcohols containing 2- or 4-pyridyl as one of the groups have been allowed to react with (+)-tartaric acid or (+)-camphor-10-sulphonic acid to form the crystalline salts. On fractional crystallisations of these salts, it has been possible to resolve isopropylphenyl-2-pyridyl and methylphenyl-4-pyridyl methanols. Attempts to resolve other seven pyridine carbinols by alkaloidal salts of half-acid ester method failed.

Preparation of ($\pm$)-Isopropylphenyl-2-pyridyl Methanol.—Phenyl-2-pyridyl ketone (36.0 g.) in ether (200 ml) was added to the Grignard complex, prepared by taking Mg(9.6 g.), isopropyl bromide (49.2 g.), and ether (75 ml); working up of the contents by the usual methods provided the crystalline carbinol (24 g.), m.p. 70-72°. Other substituted methanols, prepared similarly, are recorded in Table I along with their physical characteristics and analytical data.

TABLE I
Pyridine methanols (α - and γ -substituted).

No.	Substituted methanols.	R.	Formula.	M.P. or B.P.	n_D^{25} .	d_{20}^{25} .	[α] $_D^{25}$.	%Nitrogen.	
								Found.	Reqd.
1.	<i>n</i> -Propylphenyl-2-P	<i>n</i> -Pr	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ ON	61-62°	..	..	..	5.97	6.16
2.	Isopropylphenyl-2-P	<i>i</i> -Pr	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ ON	70-72°	..	..	+106° (c, 2.2 in chloroform)	6.08	6.16
3.	<i>n</i> -Butylphenyl-2-P	<i>n</i> -Bu	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ ON	180°/22mm	1.5630	1.2629	..	5.72	5.81
4.	Isobutylphenyl-2-P	<i>i</i> -Bu	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ON	74-74°	..	..	..	5.69	5.81
5.	Isoamylphenyl-2-P	<i>i</i> -Amyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ ON	220°/12mm	1.5540	1.2380	..	5.28	5.49
6.	Methylphenyl-4-P	Me	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ ON	148-50°	..	..	+1.58 (c, 0.45 in methanol)	6.90	7.03
7.	Isopropylphenyl-4-P	<i>i</i> -Pr	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ ON	136°	..	..	..	5.98	6.16
8.	<i>n</i> -Butylphenyl-4-P	<i>n</i> -Bu	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ON	119-20°	..	..	..	5.68	5.81
9.	Isoamylphenyl-4-P	<i>i</i> -Amyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ ON	117-18°	..	..	..	5.31	5.49

P denotes pyridyl-methanol.

Resolution of (±)-Isopropylphenyl-2-pyridyl Methanol.—(+)-Tartaric acid (15 g.) was added to a solution of (±)-isopropylphenyl-2-pyridyl methanol (22.7 g.) in warm ethanol (70 ml). The clear solution on keeping at the room temperature for 4 days separated a solid on partial decomposition; 20.1 g. (crop A), m.p. 120°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 19.7^\circ$. Crop A on further recrystallisation provided crop B (9.1 g.), m.p. 80-83°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 28.5^\circ$ on partly decomposing it. The crop B after further recrystallisation from ethanol furnished crop C (6.5 g.), m.p. 98°, which did not show any rise in rotation on further recrystallisation. The optical rotations are recorded below.

(+)-*Isopropylphenyl-2-pyridyl Methanol.*—The less soluble crop C (6.0 g.) was taken in a separating funnel containing ice-water, decomposed with sodium carbonate solution (5%), and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed, dried (Na_2SO_4), and evaporated to provide the active carbinol; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 32.08^\circ$ (c, 2.81 in acetone), m.p. 90-92°. Further recrystallisation from ether-light petroleum did not increase the rotation. The optical rotations in other solvents are shown below:

- $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 106^\circ$ (c, 2.2 in chloroform).
- $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 83^\circ$ (c, 1.06 in benzene).
- $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 81.7^\circ$ (c, 1.04 in toluene).
- $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 40.8^\circ$ (c, 0.834 in ethanol).
- $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 35.0^\circ$ (c, 0.795 in methanol).
- $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 30.3^\circ$ (c, 0.732 in dioxane)
- $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 37.7^\circ$ (c, 0.71 in methyl acetate).

(-)-*Isopropylphenyl-2-pyridyl Methanol.*—The filtrate A was decomposed after concentration to obtain the active carbinol; $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 4.4^\circ$ (c, 10.15 in methanol). It did not increase in rotation by further crystallisation.

Resolution of (±)-Methylphenylpyridyl Methanol.—(+)-Camphor-10-sulphonic acid (7 g.) was added to a solution of (±)-methylphenyl-4-pyridyl methanol (6 g.) in warm ethanol (36 ml). The clear solution after keeping at the room temperature for 2 days deposited crop A (10.2 g.), m.p. 174.5°. It was taken in ethanol (26 ml) and set aside when it furnished crop B (8.35 g.), m.p. 179-81°. The crop B on further recrystallisation afforded crop C; m.p. 185-86° (4.8 g.).

(+)-*Methylphenyl-4-pyridyl Methanol.*—The less soluble crop C (4.8 g.) on decomposition by sodium carbonate (5%) provided the active carbinol; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 1.567^\circ$ (c, 9.45 in methanol); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 2.114^\circ$ (c, 0.62 in benzene); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 1.765^\circ$ (c, 0.34 in toluene); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 3.08^\circ$ (c, 3.982 in chloroform); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 1.13^\circ$ (c, 7.13 in ethanol).

(-)-*Methylphenyl-4-pyridyl Methanol.*—The more soluble fraction on concentration and on decomposition furnished the carbinol, m.p. 145°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 0.2^\circ$ (c, 5.3 in chloroform).

Van Camper² recorded m.p. of (±)-methylphenyl-4-pyridyl methanol as 140-42°.

The IR spectra of these carbinols were taken on a Beckman IR 4, by the courtesy of Saldter Research Laboratories, Philadelphia-2, PA.

Reactions of these pyridyl carbinol with 1-chloro-2-dimethylamino-ethanol (in inert solvent in presence of sodamide) are in progress.

The authors wish to express their thanks to the C. S. I. R., New Delhi, for a junior research fellowship for some period to one of them (U.S.P.) and also to the Gujarat University for the fellowship for the remaining period.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY SCHOOL OF SCIENCES,
GUJARAT UNIVERSITY,
AHMEDABAD-0.

Received April 22, 1964.

